

The ICC, Belfast
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Effect of Viscosity Development in the Infusion Process of Composites

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LIQUID MOULDING PROCESSES

Vacuum

Resin infusion under flexible tooling

LIQUID MOULDING APPLICATIONS

RTM

VIM

Wind Turbine Blade, Vacuum infusion

RIFT

Mould

Mandrel

RIFT

VISCOSITY OF EPOXY

VISCOSITY OF EPOXY—IMPREGNATION

Stitched tows in a mat

Fibres in a tow

Glass fiber

Human hair

Carbon fiber

VISCOSITY OF EPOXY— IMPREGNATION

VISCOSITY OF EPOXY

CHALLENGES AHEAD

SGRE: SG 14-236 DD
115 meter blade length
236 m rotor diameter

GE: Haliade-X 14.7 MW-220
107 meter blade length
220 m rotor diameter

CHALLENGES AHEAD

Dry spots in wind turbine blades can be as long as 1m!

Maintenance is done after the infusion process

This maintenance can take the same time as the infusion itself!

Dry spots in wind turbine blades

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

4 layers of plain weave GF
4 inlets ports, single inlet
from the main epoxy pot
Peel ply on top
Sealant tape and vacuum bag
Application of vacuum

Outlet vent

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Filling of the mould , Experimental data

NUMERICAL SIMULATION

- Meshing for Mould filling analysis
- 48K number of Tetra elements
- 2D shell model

NUMERICAL SIMULATION

VALIDATION

VALIDATION

CONCLUSION

- A non-linear viscosity development of resin studied
- Infusion process was performed in a prototype mould
- A numerical simulation was conducted for the same mould
- Very good agreement was found between the non-linear simulations and the experimental infusion.

THANKS FOR
YOUR
ATTENTION

